

Average Acceleration for a Particle in an Infinite Well?

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A classical free particle has a specific momentum p and kinetic energy $pp/2m$. In an ideal gas with no potential $P(p)=P(-p)$ so p average=0 at each x . A quantum free particle has a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$, a specific momentum of p and a kinetic energy of $pp/2m$. A special feature seems to be that $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a length proportional to $1/p$ which repeats itself. We argue that this length is associated with the motion p in one dimension together with the two dimensionality. In other words, motion is not a simple translation. If a particle is placed in an infinite well of 1 dimension and length L , then low bound states have a special length (wavelength) of the order of the box. In other words one does not know at which point the particle is located or whether it has already reflected. Thus we argue that from a probabilistic point of view one must include p and $-p$ together. These have different probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ because this is a dynamic probability. The interference of the two removes one dimension exposing the periodic $\cos(px)$ like nature. If one calculates $pp/2m$ average using $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W$ (where W is the wavefunction) one obtains $pp/2m$ (the classical result) because both p and $-p$ have the same magnitude. The dynamic probability, however, does not have the same value for each. Thus p average = $-i \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ is not zero and this result still holds if one multiplies by W^*W . In other words there at each x there seems to be more weight to p or to $-p$. This suggests that an average acceleration may appear in fact: $\frac{d}{dx} \left\{ -\frac{dW}{dx} / W \right\} = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W - (dW/dx / W)(dW/dx / W)$.

The quantum bound scenario is a statistical one with an inherent physical (we argue) kind of motion linked to a wavelength. If a particle is knocked out of bound state it has a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ and a momentum p . It is no longer in a hybrid interfering statistical state. The modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ is 1 at each x as well. Furthermore $P(p)=P(-p) = a^*(p)a(p)=a^*(-p)a(-p)$ which is not the same result as $\exp(ipx)$ versus $\exp(-ipx)$ for the dynamical probability. Given $P(p)=P(-p)$ and no knowledge of x one might guess that one has a constant spatial density classical scenario, but this is not the case. As a result a special type of measurement is needed to discern $W^*(x)W(x)$ it seems, but this picture of humps and low probability regions is also in keeping with an average acceleration we argue.

Dynamic Probability

Quantum mechanics seems to introduce two levels of probability. First there is the dynamic probability or wavefunction of a free particle $\exp(ipx)$. Three striking features are that it is different for p and $-p$ i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ which is fine because these have different motion (to the right and left), it is not local in the sense that there is a length proportional to $1/p$ associated with the motion, but at the same time it is two dimensional so that locality is restored through the modulus which is 1 at each x . If $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability then it adds in OR situations which allows for interference which may reveal the presence of the length proportional to $1/p$, but this is an average situation. If one actually determines the specific $\exp(ipx)$ in the sum (i.e. wavefunction collapse) then one has $\exp(ipx)$ which has a modulus of 1, a momentum of p and a kinetic energy of $pp/2m$ just like a classical particle. In fact, for a particle in a box, the

wavefunction proportional to $\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)$ x in $(0,L)$ has $a(p)a(p) = a(-p)a(-p) = P(p)$. In other words using $P(p)$, p and $-p$ have the same probability (just like a coin with heads or tails), but dynamically they do not, one has $\exp(ipx)$ and the other $\exp(-ipx)$. In particular one may obtain the momentum from the dynamic probability by applying an operator namely $-i d/dx$. In classical statistical mechanics, the probability is simply a number just like $P(p) = P(-p)$. One does not operate on it to obtain dynamic information.

Relationship Between Spatial Density and Average Momentum

As seen above $P(p)$ may equal $P(-p)$ where $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ and $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. If $P(p) = P(-p)$ this mimics a classical statistical mechanical scenario, but the conclusion that one has constant spatial density is not correct. There is another probability $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. This leads to density regions with a hump and regions with almost no spatial density. $W(x)$ is linked to $\exp(ipx)$ which in turn is linked to dynamics. $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional so that its modulus is 1 at each x , but if interference (i.e. an OR probability) occurs one does not know which momentum one has and the modulus of 1 property no longer holds. Even a particle moving to the right and left have different dynamic probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ revealing the special length proportional to $1/p$. As a result it is the interference essentially of p and $-p$ which yield the spatial density so $P(x)$ and dynamic probabilities of p and $-p$ at x are strongly linked (in fact $\text{ave at } x = -i dW/dx / W$). $P(p)$ on the other hand represents a second average of p ave at x over all of x so that one loses information about the crests and troughs. E.g. $\text{Integral } dx \ (-idW/dx / W) W = \text{Sum over } p \ p \ P(p)$.

For a particle in an infinite well we argue that the changing density is linked to a changing p ave at x i.e. there is a kind of average acceleration in the picture. How is this possible if KE average at x is a constant $= -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W = pp/2m$? Both p and $-p$ have the same magnitude, but different dynamical probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. Thus the average p at x i.e.

$$\{p \exp(ipx) + (-p)\exp(-ipx)\} / \{\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)\} \text{ is not } 0 \text{ suggesting a favoring of either } p \text{ or } -p \quad ((1))$$

As one moves from one x to another the favoring changes suggesting a kind of acceleration. In particular,:

$$\text{Magnitude}(P \text{ ave at } x) = p \cos(px) / \sin(px) \text{ for } x \text{ in } (0,L) \quad ((2))$$

One may multiply this by $W^*W = \sin(px) \sin(px) C1 C1$ to obtain an average multiplied by density. This density depends on the interference of the dynamic probabilities of p and $-p$ in the first place. Thus one is multiplying two averages together. To see average acceleration explicitly one may compute:

$$d/dx \{dW/dx / W\} = d/dx dW/dx / W - \{dW/dx / W\}\{dW/dx / W\} \quad ((3))$$

The first term is $\langle p \rangle$ while the second is related to the square of $\langle p \rangle$. Overall this is a function of x .

Thus what would classically be a scenario of a particle moving to the right during one time interval with p and $p^2/2m$ and then to the left during another time interval with $-p$ and $p^2/2m$ becomes an interference of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ which suggests average acceleration and a spatial density. It seems, however, that a special measurement is needed to discern the density because $P(\langle p \rangle) = \langle p \rangle^2 P(\langle p \rangle)$ only yields a probability about $\langle p \rangle$ with no information about x .

{One may note that we use $P(\langle p \rangle)$ because although all p values contribute to $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ for the infinite well problem, there is no variance i.e. $\sum_p p^2 P(p) = P(\langle p \rangle) P(\langle p \rangle)$. One may also note that $\langle p \rangle$ is the average magnitude in one direction i.e. $P(\langle p \rangle) = P(-\langle p \rangle)$ so the overall average momentum is 0. This also follows from:

$$\int dx W^* W (-i \hbar dW/dx / W) = C \int dx \sin(\langle p \rangle x) (-i \langle p \rangle) \cos(\langle p \rangle x) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

In other words quantum mechanics picks out spatial details within a special length proportional to $1/p$ because this length is of the same order of the system i.e. the box with the well. If the size of the box is large and $1/p$ very small and one has bad resolution, one would not detect these quantum features i.e. crests and troughs.

Quantum Features mixed with Classical

As argued above quantum mechanics is linked to a dynamic probability $\exp(ipx)$ which through interference brings in a spatial density of crests and troughs and is linked with average acceleration even in the case of a particle in an infinite well. These seem to be purely quantum results. One may ask why one should have interference of p and $-p$ when they are clearly separated in time in a classical situation. As mentioned in previous notes, given that there is a length proportional to $1/p$ associated with linear motion, one does not really know where the particle is within that length. If this length is of the order of the system it is quite possible that the particle has bounced off the infinite potential wall and is now $-p$. Thus for lower energy states one must consider the probability of p and $-p$ together.

It is interesting to note that although $\exp(ipx)$ brings in completely quantum features, a classical constraint is placed on average kinetic energy for all energy levels i.e.

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} / W + V(x) = E_n \quad \text{where} \quad \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} / W = KE_{\text{classical}}(x) \quad ((5))$$

Thus even though $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $-i \hbar dW/dx / W$ are behaving in unusual quantum ways, the average kinetic is not. Even though $dW/dx / W$ suggests more of p or $-p$ at each x , p^2 is the same for p and $-p$ in an infinite well and there is no reason to expect $p^2/2m$ to deviate from a constant. This is interesting because:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{\exp(ipx)}{\exp(ipx)} = \frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{\exp(-ipx)}{\exp(-ipx)} = \frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{\{\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)\}}{\{\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)\}} \quad ((6))$$

In other words $p^2/2m$ does not distinguish between p and $-p$ and so even if these have different dynamical probabilities, the overall OR result does not distinguish either.

For the infinite well, the solution $C_1 \sin(pave x)$ has the same height of peaks throughout the box. Thus if one draws a line touching the peaks it is horizontal suggesting a classical result, namely a constant spatial density. In the case of a potential $V(x)$ peaks again appear (e.g. oscillator), but these have different heights. As the energy level n increases, these heights match an envelope described by $C_2/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity from $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 + V(x) = E$. $C_2/v(x)$ is related to the amount of time a classical particle spends in a fixed dx which then is taken to be the interpretation of the quantum density $W^*(x)W(x)$ (or rather its envelope) as well.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that quantum mechanics is based on a dynamical free particle probability $\exp(ipx)$ which differs for p and $-p$ (due to the different dynamics). In particular one may operate on this probability with $-i\hbar d/dx$ to obtain momentum, something one does not do in classical probability theory. If one has a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$'s as in the case of a potential (even for a particle in a box with infinite walls) then $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and $dW/dx / W$ is proportional to the average momentum at a point. Furthermore $W^*(x)W(x)$ is spatial density so there is a strong connection between a dynamical free particle probability and spatial density. $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ which for a particle in a box is the same for p and $-p$, but $\exp(ipave x)$ and $\exp(-ipave x)$ are not. This allows the periodic features (i.e. a characteristic length proportional to $1/p$) to be exposed by adding $\exp(ipave x)$ to $-\exp(-ipave x)$. This in turn depends on the two dimensional structure of $\exp(ipx)$ which allows one to have nonlocality in each dimension i.e a characteristic length proportional to $1/p$ and yet to have a modulus of 1 at each x which indicates the same momentum impulse at each point. Again one is speaking of probabilities.

For a particle in a box, the characteristic length proportional to $1/p$ is of the same order as the box size for low energy levels and so one cannot distinguish whether a particle is moving forward or backwards as in classical mechanics. One must use probability and include both. We argue that the differences in $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-px)$ lead to a nonzero OR situation unlike classical statistical mechanics. This OR or addition changes with x implying a kind of average acceleration. For a particle in an infinite well, this is given by: $d/dx \{dW/dx / W\} = KE(x)_{\text{classical}} - \{dW/dx / W\} \{dW/dx / W\}$ where $KE(x)_{\text{classical}} = p^2/2m$ in this case. Thus even though the particle is moving with a constant average p , one may have p or $-p$ at each x point with different weights and this gives the semblance of an acceleration and is in keeping with the unusual crest spatial density. $P(p) = P(-p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ is classical in nature and describes an equal overall probability for p and $-p$ over the length of the box, but at each x the scenario is very different. Just seeing $P(p) = P(-p)$ one would guess a constant spatial density as in classical statistical mechanics, but that is not the case.

It should be noted that a quantum particle in an infinite well system is often described in terms of statistical mechanics with an amount of energy added and the particle occupying different energy states with different probabilities. In such cases, the spatial pattern and acceleration are

usually ignored and an average pressure calculated proportional to $\int dp \rho P(\rho) = \int dx W (-d/dx)d/dx W$ used. In this note we wish to examine the internal average acceleration as it describes a somewhat different picture we argue.